

Superclomeleon biosensor-based assay for SLC26A9 using HEK293 SLC26A9 JumpIn OE cells

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Assay description

SuperClomeleon is a Cl^- sensitive ratiometric FRET (Fluorescence Resonance Energy Transfer) sensor obtained by fusing a YFP mutant (Yellow Fluorescent Protein, that is a yellow variant of the GFP with a high sensitivity towards halides) and the Cyan Fluorescent Protein (CFP, insensitive to halides) (Figure 1). Intracellular increase of Cl^- finally leads to a decrease of the FRET ratio YFP/CFP. SLC26A9 is involved in diverse transport modes in different systems and especially is a highly selective Cl^- transporter: Chloride fluxes through SLC26A9 lead to Superclomeleon FRET signal changes that can be monitored.

Figure 1. Principal of a Superclomeleon biosensor assay. Superclomeleon is based on the coupling of CFP and YFP via a flexible peptide linker. The ratio of fluorescence emission of the YFP acceptor to that of the CFP donor depended on the concentration of potassium chloride. Chloride induced decrease in the FRET efficiency is due to a selective quenching of YFP fluorescence: YFP fluorescence was sensitive to Chloride, while it had no significant effect on the fluorescence emitted by the CFP.

Assay protocol

To develop a functional recombinant SLC26A9 cell-based assay, HEK-293 cells were stably transfected with the SLC26A9 coding sequence. Mock control (transfected with the empty plasmid) was generated in parallel. Two rounds of limiting dilution led to the isolation of pure clones, the final clone was subjected to pharmacological characterization and tested to verify that the assay fulfils HTS quality criteria in terms of robustness and reproducibility.

Cell preparation

Cells were detached from 70-80% confluent flasks and transiently transfected with Superclomeleon biosensor expressing construct. Transfection was performed in suspension, using the Lipofectamine 2000 method following manufacturer's instruction. Cells were seeded at 20'000 cells/well in black-clear bottom poly-D-Lysine coated 384 well plate in complete medium and incubated 24 hours at 37°C, 5% CO_2 .

Superclomeleon assay

Medium was removed and cells were incubated at RT in 20 μL /well of Chloride free buffer and plates analysed at Hamamatsu FDSS7000EX reader using a CFP/YFP filter (exc: 438 nm for CFP stimulation, 542nm and 483nm emissions for YFP and CFP respectively).

To test pharmacology different concentrations of Chloride ((0 mM – 15 mM – 30 mM – 45 mM – 60 mM – 75 mM – 90 mM – 100 mM) 10 μL /well as 3X; 0.5% DMSO final concentration) were online injected at the plate reader.

To test the effect of Niflumic acid as potential SLC26A9 inhibitor, cells were preincubated in Chloride free buffer \pm 500 μM Niflumic acid for 5 minutes, then different concentrations of Chloride were online injected at the plate reader and YFP/CFP ratio recorded.

To assess robustness, reproducibility and amenability to high-throughput screening in single injection protocol, three 384-well plates were run consecutively, using the following plate layout (Figure 2).

- Col 1 and 24 Chloride dose response curve
- Col 2 to 23 Chloride EC_{50} (100 mM)
- Col 2 to 23 Neutral Control (0% Activity): +0.5% DMSO

Data analysis

Hamamatsu FDSS7000EX measurements were analysed by using the Hamamatsu software (FDSS7000EX/ μ CELL software U8524-03A). Data were exported as Area Under the Curve (AUC) values of Ratio YFP/CFP.

Mean and standard deviation of each replicate were calculated on the exported data with Excel software, then values were used to create sigmoidal dose-response curves (variable slope) and to calculate EC_{50}/IC_{50} values with GraphPad PRISM software (Version 8).

Additional information

Target data

SLC	SLC26A9
Synonyms	Anion Transporter/Exchanger Protein 9
SLC sub-family	Solute Carrier Family 26 (Anion Exchanger)
UniProt ID	Q7LBE3
RESOLUTE Cell ID	HEK-293/SLC26A9 K3.3 p4 (Axxam cell line)

Assay data

<p>The graph shows the FRET: YFP/CFP ratio on the y-axis (ranging from -80 to 0) against the log concentration of Cl⁻ in M on the x-axis (ranging from -2.5 to -0.5). Three data series are plotted: 'mock + Niflumic acid' (green triangles), 'mock' (black circles), and 'SLC26A9 + Niflumic acid' (blue inverted triangles). A red line with square markers represents 'SLC26A9' alone. The SLC26A9 curve shows a significant decrease in the FRET ratio as Cl⁻ concentration increases, which is partially inhibited by the addition of Niflumic acid.</p>	<p>(i.e EC50, PoC, etc)</p>	<p>The highest concentration of tested NaCl (100 mM) showed a 400% higher Cl⁻ influx in the target cells, compared to wt cells</p>
<p>The RZ factor plot shows the RZ value on the y-axis (ranging from -0.5 to 1.0) for three plates on the x-axis. The RZ values are approximately 0.48, 0.42, and 0.42 for plates 1, 2, and 3, respectively, all falling below the 0.5 threshold.</p>	<p>Compound name (2)</p> <p>PubChem CID</p> <p>Vendor (catalogue #)</p> <p>Mode of action</p> <p>Standard value type (i.e EC50, PoC, etc)</p>	<p>Niflumic acid</p> <p>4488</p> <p>ChemCruz, #sc-204820</p> <p>Inhibitor</p> <p>PoC = 120%. Only one concentration tested, 500 μM, which showed more than 30% of specific SLC inhibition (no effect on wt cells)</p>
<p>The Intraplate Variability plot shows variability on the y-axis (ranging from -30 to 30) for three plates on the x-axis. Blue squares represent CR and yellow triangles represent SR. Variability values are generally low, mostly within the -15 to 15 range.</p>	<p>RZ' factor calculated as</p> $RZ' = 1 - \frac{3 \cdot RSD(CR_p) + 3 \cdot RSD(SR_p)}{ (CR_p) - (SR_p) }$ <p>in single injection protocol</p>	<p>RZ' factor calculated as</p> $RZ' = 1 - \frac{3 \cdot RSD(CR_p) + 3 \cdot RSD(SR_p)}{ (CR_p) - (SR_p) }$ <p>in single injection protocol</p>
<p>The Interplate Variability plot shows variability on the y-axis (ranging from -30 to 30) for three plates on the x-axis. Blue squares represent CR and yellow triangles represent SR. Variability values are higher than in the intraplate plot, with some points reaching up to 25.</p>	<p>Intraplate Variability calculated as</p> $\text{Variability Intraplate}_{CR} = \frac{SD(CR_p)}{ SR_p - CR_p } \times 100$ $\text{Variability Intraplate}_{SR} = \frac{SD(SR_p)}{ SR_p - CR_p } \times 100$ <p>in single injection protocol</p>	<p>Intraplate Variability calculated as</p> $\text{Variability Intraplate}_{CR} = \frac{SD(CR_p)}{ SR_p - CR_p } \times 100$ $\text{Variability Intraplate}_{SR} = \frac{SD(SR_p)}{ SR_p - CR_p } \times 100$ <p>in single injection protocol</p>
<p>The Interplate Variability plot shows variability on the y-axis (ranging from -30 to 30) for three plates on the x-axis. Blue squares represent CR and yellow triangles represent SR. Variability values are higher than in the intraplate plot, with some points reaching up to 25.</p>	<p>Interplate Variability calculated as</p> $\text{Variability Interplate}_{CR} = \frac{CR_p - \text{mean}(CR_{p,d})}{ CR_{p,d} - SR_{p,d} } \times 100$ $\text{Variability Interplate}_{SR} = \frac{SR_p - \text{mean}(SR_{p,d})}{ CR_{p,d} - SR_{p,d} } \times 100$ <p>in single injection protocol</p>	<p>Interplate Variability calculated as</p> $\text{Variability Interplate}_{CR} = \frac{CR_p - \text{mean}(CR_{p,d})}{ CR_{p,d} - SR_{p,d} } \times 100$ $\text{Variability Interplate}_{SR} = \frac{SR_p - \text{mean}(SR_{p,d})}{ CR_{p,d} - SR_{p,d} } \times 100$ <p>in single injection protocol</p>

Discussion

The Superclomeleon biosensor assay for SLC26A9 showed a strong, specific and dose-dependent FRET signal decrease in target cells, suggesting the internalization of Chloride. Niflumic acid treatment led to a reduced FRET signal decrease upon Chloride injection, suggesting that SLC26A9 mediated Chloride transport is partially inhibited by Niflumic acid.

The assay fulfils the HTS quality criteria.

Cross references

- RESOLUTE report at [Zenodo](#).